

TRANSFORMING TULANG BAWANG MPP SERVICES THROUGH CHANGE MODELS AND BUSINESS PROCESS REDESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The operation of Public Service Mall (MPP) in Indonesia is frequently constrained by service fragmentation, ego-sectarianism, and unaligned business processes, despite integrating various agencies into a single location. This study aims to construct a business process redesign mechanism as an instrument to strengthen service quality at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP. A qualitative approach with an explanative single-case study design was employed, utilizing in-depth interviews, observations, and documentation. The results indicate that service transformation does not occur linearly but through a mixed governance mechanism that combines formal procedures with adaptive, informal coordination among actors in the field. Service digitalization serves as the primary driving factor forcing organizations to implement an Empirical Model of Business Process Redesign Mechanisms. This model consists of seven circular stages: initial condition, triggers, drivers, socio-technical systems, change mechanisms, business process redesign, and optimization outcomes. In conclusion, public service optimization is not merely a technical-digital intervention. Instead, it is the product of a harmonious interaction between actor capacity, institutional legitimacy, and adaptive technological systems to ensure sustainable governance.

Keywords: Public Service Mall, Business Process Redesign, Change Mechanism, Digital Transformation, Service Governance.

INTRODUCTION

The provision of public services is a manifestation of the fundamental role of government in realizing responsive and accountable governance. In Indonesia, the urgency of strengthening service quality is constructed as part of the bureaucratic reform policy direction through innovation and institutional restructuring. Nevertheless, empirical literature still highlights a linear gap between regulation and implementation; the quality of public services is currently being tested by challenges surrounding efficiency, effectiveness, and low connectivity among stakeholders (Rahayu et al., 2022; Ali et al., 2023).

Based on global governance assessments, the quality of governance in Indonesia is currently categorized as moderate. This is reflected in the achievements of the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), which confirm that bureaucratic effectiveness has not run at its maximum capacity (World Bank, 2023). In line with these findings, the

2023 Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) report also emphasizes the urgency of strengthening aspects of accountability and transparency within the public service sector (Transparency International, 2023). This phenomenon serves as evidence that structural problems in public services do not merely stem from administrative matters, but are closely related to institutional structure problems, weak cross-sectoral coordination, and unintegrated service business processes.

To solve these problems, the one-stop service paradigm, such as the *Mal Pelayanan Publik* (MPP), has begun to be widely implemented, including in Indonesia. Through the integration of cross-sectoral services in a single, digitally-based centralized location, this model is projected to optimize efficiency, transparency, and accessibility for the public (Megawati et al., 2025; Ekayasa, 2025). Empirically, the presence of MPP is capable of escalating service quality and internal process effectiveness through data consolidation and inter-agency harmonization, although it still faces constraints regarding human resource capacity, collaborative governance, and system synchronization (Rahayu et al., 2022).

However, the essence of integrated public services is not limited to the physical unification of institutions within a single operational space. Its success is fundamentally determined by the maturity level of business process integration, information system architecture, and the effectiveness of collaboration among stakeholders. Various literatures indicate that the absence of adequate process and governance integration has the potential to degrade public service performance achievements within such integrated service systems (Megawati et al., 2025; Ekayasa, 2025).

The lack of continuous presence of institutional apparatus at the MPP triggers a reduction in service quantity, while simultaneously unveiling underlying issues within the coordination, integration, and continuity of the program. This phenomenon confirms that the unification of public services is not merely a matter of infrastructure and facilities provision, but is heavily determined by the persistent involvement of the respective institutional actors. The decline in attendance intensity signals a drop in institutional participation within the integrated service ecosystem, directly impacting the lack of service diversification and the dwindling public interest. This condition is further exacerbated by significant disparities in the distribution of service workloads among agencies.

Figure 1. *Distribution of Service Types at Public Service Malls in Tulang Bawang Regency, 2018–2025*

Source: Research Documentation, 2026

The data presented in Figure 1. illustrates a striking disparity in services, where contributions are heavily dominated by specific work units while the roles of other institutions remain highly minimal. This phenomenon indicates that service governance is still sectorally fragmented and has not yet achieved an ideal degree of integration. Specifically, there remains a gap in scientific discourse regarding how business process redesign formulations are executed amid a complex public environment laden with the interests of various actors and institutions. The facts in Tulang Bawang Regency reinforce that public service evaluation must move beyond final outcomes by also highlighting the processes and turbulence of change during implementation.

Addressing the limitations of prior research, this study aims to construct a business process redesign mechanism as an instrument to strengthen services at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP. The orientation of this study is not limited to the quantification of performance achievements, but rather focuses on the reconstruction of the change processes occurring within the service bureaucracy. The perspective employed views the success of the MPP as a product of a tripartite interaction among business process standardization, institutional capacity, and the behavior of implementing actors. Therefore, the primary direction of this research is to systematically explain the course of the change process in business process redesign and to detect the influence of its mechanism on improving the quality of public services

LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Public Service and Service Quality

Public service is a core function of government and a reflection of governance quality manifested through the interaction between the state and society. This concept has continuously transformed alongside paradigm shifts in public administration—moving from rule-bound Old Public Administration to efficiency-driven New Public Management, and ultimately to the participatory responsiveness of New Public Service. This evolution confirms that service orientation has shifted from mere procedural compliance toward enhancing quality and public satisfaction.

Theoretically, service quality is measured through dimensions such as speed, accessibility, and procedural clarity. The SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry) operationalizes this into five core indicators: *tangibles*, *reliability*, *responsiveness*, *assurance*, and *empathy*. However, optimizing these dimensions cannot be achieved solely at the front-office level. Bottlenecks such as inefficient business processes, convoluted bureaucracies, and weak cross-unit coordination frequently serve as the root causes of poor service performance. Consequently, improving public service quality requires a comprehensive approach that combines transactional service excellence with business process redesign and supportive institutional structures.

Business Process and Business Process Redesign

A business process is a structured and integrated sequence of activities designed to generate value for service users. In modern management, business processes are viewed not merely as operational workflows, but as dynamic systems that connect resources, information, technology, and organizational actors to deliver valuable outputs (Davenport, 1993; Dumas et al., 2018). Therefore, the business process serves as a crucial unit of analysis for measuring and understanding organizational performance.

In the evolution of modern management, Business Process Management (BPM) and Business Process Reengineering (BPR) have emerged as primary strategies for organizational performance enhancement. BPM focuses on incremental and continuous process improvement, whereas BPR emphasizes radical overhaul to achieve breakthroughs in efficiency, quality, and service speed (Hammer & Champy, 1993; Rosemann & vom Brocke, 2015). Rather than being dichotomous, these two approaches complement each other in driving process-based organizational transformation.

This transformative synergy becomes highly critical within the context of integrated public services like the *Mal Pelayanan Publik* (MPP). Although the one-stop service concept has successfully unified various agencies physically, the essence of service integration fundamentally relies on business process alignment and information system interoperability across institutions (Rahayu et al., 2022; Megawati et al., 2025). Without internal process integration and robust coordination, operational activities at the MPP will remain trapped in sectoral silos that fail to deliver added value to the public.

To address this challenge, this study positions business process redesign not merely as a rigid managerial tool, but as a dynamic and contextual process of change. Therefore, the analysis in this study is specifically directed to unraveling the mechanisms of business

process transition, mapping the interactions among the actors and institutions that influence it, and formulating how these mechanisms contribute tangibly to optimizing MPP services.

The Concept of Mechanism in Organizational Change

The concept of a causal mechanism in the social sciences is an approach that traces specific processes and interactions to explain *how* and *why* a cause produces an effect, moving beyond simple correlations between variables (Hedström & Swedberg, 1998). This mechanism is understood as a dynamic constellation of entities, such as actors or structures, and activities, such as interactions or processes, working in tandem to bring about a specific outcome (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010). This approach is paramount in organizational and public policy domains, given that change processes are rarely linear or deterministic; rather, they are laden with actor negotiations, regulatory adaptations, and the dialectic between formal and informal structures. Consequently, the success of a policy is determined not only by its design on paper, but by how the implementation mechanism manifests and adapts within local institutional and social contexts (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010).

In management contexts, this mechanistic logic linearly underpins the success of business process redesign. Redesigning does not stop at altering formal procedures; instead, it transforms actor interaction patterns, aligns organizational structures, and integrates technological systems to generate better efficiency and service quality (Dumas et al., 2018). This urgency is increasingly evident in the MPP ecosystem, which involves complex cross-agency, multi-actor, and multi-system relationships. Integrated public service does not automatically materialize through the mere physical merging of counters under a one-stop service concept; it must be driven by substantive coordination mechanisms, procedural adjustments, and field-level technological interoperability (Rahayu et al., 2022; Megawati et al., 2025). Therefore, the analysis of integrated services at the MPP must look beneath surface-level outcomes to trace how rules are translated into practice and how socio-technical systems adapt to change.

Grounded in this conceptual framework, this study positions the concept of mechanism as the primary analytical lens to dissect how business process redesign transforms public service quality at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP. This mechanism is framed as the product of a dynamic tripartite interaction among implementing actors, institutional structures, and socio-technical systems in navigating the bureaucratic transition. Through this causal approach, the study moves beyond the mere quantification of final outputs or service performance metrics. Instead, it is directed toward providing a contextual explanation of the change process within the bureaucracy, while identifying the key factors that dictate the success or failure of business process redesign in MPP operations.

METHODS

Research Approach and Type

This study applies an explanative qualitative single-case study design using within-case analysis to holistically investigate the internal characteristics of the Tulang Bawang

Regency MPP without cross-regional comparisons (Creswell, 2018). This approach is selected to capture actor perspectives and scrutinize real-world dynamics where boundaries between institutional networks and technology adoption are not clearly distinct. Moving beyond surface-level descriptions, its explanative nature systematically clarifies *how* and *why* business process changes occur, the factors driving them, and how these relationships shape public service quality. With the MPP as the locus, the unit of analysis encompasses business processes, actors, institutional factors, socio-technical systems, and change mechanisms. Ultimately, this design is ideal for providing a contextual, deep, and comprehensive explanation of causal relationships and transitional dynamics in integrated public service delivery.

Research Location and Data Sources

This research was conducted at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP as the study locus, selected purposively due to its alignment with the investigated phenomena, such as declining user numbers, decreasing participating agencies, and service dominance by specific work units. According to Creswell (2018), contextually defining a qualitative research location is crucial for achieving a deep understanding of a phenomenon. To deconstruct these dynamics, this study integrates primary and secondary data to ensure analytical validity and depth. Primary data—noted by Miles and Huberman (1994) as fundamental for capturing the experiences, perspectives, and social interactions of actors—were gathered directly through in-depth interviews and observations of the business redesign process, involving key informants (DPMPTSP officials, agency/OPD representatives, front-line staff, service users, policymakers, as well as legislative, academic, and private sector stakeholders). Meanwhile, secondary data (comprising official MPP documents, performance reports, user and agency statistical data, public service regulations, and prior literature) were utilized in parallel as supporting instruments for empirical mapping and triangulation to strengthen the comprehensive analysis of change mechanisms.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Informant selection in this study was carried out purposively (and expanded via snowball sampling techniques) to capture cross-sectoral actors who experience and are directly involved in the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP ecosystem. The spectrum of informants was broadened to include: (1) technical agency officials (DPMPTSP, Disdukcapil, Kemenag, Polres, Kejaksaan, KP2KP), (2) policymakers (Bappeda and the Organizational Division), (3) front-office staff, (4) service users, (5) legislators, (6) public service observers (academics, LSM, and community organizations), and (7) private/external partners (banking, business actors, and IT sectors). In line with Creswell (1995), collecting data from multiple sources is vital to enhance validity through triangulation. This was operationalized through three techniques: semi-structured in-depth interviews to capture actor perspectives (Kvale, 1996); direct observation of service delivery workflows and natural social interactions (Spradley, 1980); and documentation (reports, SOPs, regulations, statistical data) to anchor the case study context (Yin, 2000).

Subsequently, the gathered data were analyzed using a simultaneous-qualitative approach, adopting the flow model of Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña (2014), which encompasses data reduction, data display (matrices, tables, charts), and drawing explanative conclusions. This process was deepened through mechanism analysis to map the causal interactions among actors, institutions, and socio-technical systems; inductive typology analysis (based on field findings) to categorize integration variations; and integrative analysis to synthesize the final empirical model based on theoretical propositions. The entire analytical sequence progressed systematically from open/axial coding to model formulation. To ensure trustworthiness, the study employed four validation strategies: source triangulation across various actor perspectives (Denzin, 1978); method triangulation integrating interviews, observations, and documents (Creswell, 2018); member checking to confirm the accuracy of the researcher's interpretations (Miles & Huberman, 1994); and referential adequacy utilizing secondary data as an empirical baseline.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Initial Conditions and Service Structure of the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP

This section maps the existing conditions of the Tulang Bawang Regency Mal Pelayanan Publik (MPP) as a baseline to explore the mechanisms of service change in depth. Based on the results of interviews, field observations, and document reviews, the analysis focuses on current operational dynamics, major field constraints, the empirical experiences of both officers and users, and service weaknesses. As a one-stop integrated service center, Figure 2 documents that this MPP encompasses a total of 198 service types. Nevertheless, the distribution pattern reveals a sharp disparity, as services are heavily concentrated within the DPMPTSP (117 services), the Kementerian Agama (25 services), and the Disdukcapil (23 services), whereas the contributions of partner agencies such as BPJS, KP2KP, Polres, Imigrasi, BPOM, and the banking sector remain relatively limited. This phenomenon demonstrates that although the physical and institutional unification of the MPP appears extensive on the surface, the integration has not yet proceeded in a balanced manner and has not touched substantive aspects at the level of business process coordination or digital system interconnection.

Figure 2. Composition of MPP Services in Tulang Bawang Regency

Source: Research Documentation, 2026

This data structure reveals a glaring disparity in service distribution due to the overwhelming dominance of the DPMPTSP. This phenomenon indicates that although the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP has successfully onboarded numerous institutions, the actual institutional integration established is not yet fully equitable. Consequently, this initial condition baseline proves that the physical expansion of service coverage remains unaligned with its operational reality. In practice, the delivery of integrated public services at the Tulang Bawang MPP is still hindered by various fundamental limitations in data system synchronization, the quality of cross-agency coordination, and socio-technical readiness, which cumulatively obstruct the achievement of truly integrated service optimization.

Business Process Redesign Mechanisms in Service Optimization

This constructs a comprehensive synthesis of the dynamic relationships among actors, institutions, socio-technical systems, and business processes at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP based on data triangulation. According to the conceptual framework in Figure 3, the transformation ecosystem is depicted as a linear governance process moving from the upstream *Initial Service Conditions* (fragmented, sectoral, manual) toward the downstream *Service Optimization*. This cycle is driven by *Change Triggers* stemming from national regulations and efficiency demands, which are structurally responded to by the *Change Driver* components (Actors and Institutions). This interaction relies heavily on the reinforcement of an integrated *Socio-Technical System* that unifies the pillars of human resources, technology, and network infrastructure in the field. Through dynamic *Change Mechanisms*, this entire sequence culminates in *Business Process Redesign* measures aimed at achieving comprehensive efficiency and service integration.

Figure 3. MPP Service Business Process Redesign Mechanism

Source: Processed Research Data, 2026

Meanwhile, the dynamics of this transformation academically reflect a structured bureaucratic evolution, as mapped out in Table 1. The penetration of regulation and digitalization within the *Trigger* element acts as a pressure for change to disrupt the previously rigid bureaucratic status quo. The synergy between actor agency and institutional strengthening within the *Driver* dimension serves as the driving pillar that legitimizes the direction of operational policies. This transition is robustly supported by the Supporting System (*socio-technical support*), which facilitates coordination schemes and flexible adaptation to situational constraints in the field. This dialectic manifests in *Business Process Redesign* measures through system simplification that prunes past procedural complexities to generate high-performance *Outcomes*.

Table 1. Stages of Service Change Mechanism

Stage	Ocurring Condition	Form of Change
Initial Condition	Sectoral and manual services	Service fragmentation
Trigger	Regulation and digitalization	Pressure for change
Driver	Actor and institutions	Drivers of change
Supporting System	HR and technology	Socio-technical support
Mechanism	Coordination and adaptation	Service adjustment

Redesign	Simplification and digitalization	Business process change
Outcome	Efficiency and integration	Service optimization

Sumber: Processed Research Data, 2026

Referring to the flowchart in Figure 4, this operational governance transformation process runs sequentially through six strategic stages, from a manual model to an integrated system. At the surface level, the existence of Informal Coordination via WhatsApp effectively emerges as a flexible instrument to penetrate bureaucratic rigidity and situational constraints. This adaptive tripartite consolidation is proven to engineer new workflows that substantially prune governance complexities.

Figure 4. Service Change Flowchart

Source: Processed Research Data, 2026

Based on performance indicators, the integration of digital applications (OSS, SIMBG, Si Cantik, and Adminduk Digital) has successfully simplified front-office processes and reduced face-to-face interactions. However, this digitalization linearly triggers a new dependency on public network stability and the risk of queues during system maintenance. This phenomenon demonstrates that the quality of service outputs is heavily influenced by how the business process architecture is executed collectively. Ultimately, the business process redesign mechanism at the Tulang Bawang MPP underscores that bureaucratic reform is not limited to altering formal procedures on paper, but is significantly determined by the collaborative synergy between the sociological readiness of actors, the strength of institutional legality, and digitally-based system simplification.

The research findings reveal that business process reengineering at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP develops incrementally, adaptively, and dynamically through multi-element causal mechanisms (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010). This dynamic is driven by a hybrid governance mechanism that blends formal bureaucracy with cross-actor informal communication. This flexible relational phenomenon affirms the theories of adaptive governance (Ansell & Gash, 2008) and collaborative governance (Emerson, Nabatchi, & Balogh, 2012) in overcoming systemic rigidity. On the other hand, the organizational adaptation mechanism is stimulated by mandatory digitalization (OSS, SIMBG, Si Cantik, and Adminduk Digital), which alters the workflows of the apparatus. This non-uniform structural adjustment across agencies validates the theory of organizational adaptation (Donaldson, 2001) while reflecting the dynamic capability aspect of Teece (2007) regarding the readiness of local human resource capacity.

On a practical dimension, this transformation manifests in a business process redesign that restructures inter-institutional relationship maps through simplification and electronic approval (Hammer & Champy, 1993). However, residual fragmentation in backend processes indicates that service unification still progresses via incremental integration to maintain organizational stability (Lindblom, 1959). Although partial, the shift from physical location integration toward electronic unification proves the existence of a clear digital governance transformation trajectory (Dunleavy et al., 2006). Macro-economically, the successful performance of the MPP is a cumulative impact of the interconnectedness of structural, cultural, leadership, and technological environment dimensions (Burke, 2017). The existence of situational adjustments that are not entirely planned change reinforces Heifetz's (1994) adaptive change theory, which posits that public service optimization is the product of dynamic, transformative socio-technical interactions.

Empirical Model of Business Process Redesign Mechanisms Toward MPP Service Optimization

This empirical model is constructed based on an in-depth synthesis of interviews, observations, and field documentation to articulate that public service optimization moves evolutionarily through multi-element interactions. Referring to the comprehensive diagram in Figure 5, the entire transformation ecosystem is depicted as a gradual governance cycle rooted in the upstream *Initial Service Conditions* characterized by fragmented integration (service silos and sectoral backends). This impassability is intervened in by *Change Triggers* (national regulations and efficiency demands) that necessitate process improvement, which are then tactically responded to by *Change Drivers* through the collaboration of key actor agencies (lead agency) and the strengthening of institutional regulations (SOP). This pillar is structurally supported by the *Socio-Technical System* (HR, technology, and networks) which performs a dual role, acting both as an enabling factor and a constraining factor (asymmetric digital literacy). Through these modalities, a *Change Mechanism* (formal-informal adaptive coordination) is executed, manifesting in a *Business Process Redesign* that includes front-office simplification and electronic approval. The effectiveness of this redesign directly yields *Change Outputs* (efficiency, accessibility, transparency, physical unification) that accumulate into *Outcomes* in the form of *Incremental Service Optimization*, before ultimately culminating in strategic *Long-Term Impacts* via the *Feedback & Continuous Learning* pathway.

Figure 5. Empirical Model of the Probis Redesign Mechanism Toward Optimizing MPP Services

Source: Processed Research Data, 2026

The empirical validation of this macro-governance cycle is conceptually and academically mapped through the data interpretation instrument in Table 2. Within it, the concrete finding regarding physical counter integration that has not yet attained system unification is categorized as a characteristic of a *semi-integrated service* under the initial conditions. To consolidate the pressures of digitalization, the dominant role of the DPMPTSP is theoretically positioned as the primary driver (*lead agency*), which is reinforced by local regulatory instruments as a form of institutional support (*institutional support*). Its operational acceleration relies on the utilization of a multiple technology architecture (OSS, SIMBG, Si Cantik) as part of the socio-technical system domain (*socio-technical system*). The smoothness of daily services is bridged by informal communication pathways among officers (*adaptive coordination*) before manifesting into business process reengineering actions (*business process redesign*). This series of simultaneous alignments is concretely proven to yield a confluence of *service optimization* in the form of achieving a significantly more concise service for the public.

Table 2. Synthesis of Empirical Model Formation

Empirical Findings	Analytical Concept	Model Element
Service integration remains partial	Fragmented integration	Initial service conditions
OSS and service digitalization	Trigger perubahan	Driving factors of change
DPMPTSP as coordinator	Lead agency	Drivers of change
SOP and service regulations	Institutional support	Institutions
OSS, SIMBG, Si Cantik	Socio-technical system	Socio-technical system
Informal communication among officers	Adaptive coordination	Change mechanisms
Digital service simplification	Business process redesign	Business process redesign
Faster services	Service optimization	Output dan outcome

Source: Processed Research Data, 2026

The causal relationship mechanism among the variables forming the model above is visualized sequentially through the flowchart in Figure 6. This conceptual design demonstrates that the ACTOR element at the top and the SOCIO-TECHNICAL SYSTEM element at the bottom move simultaneously to provide a direct contribution to the INSTITUTIONAL pillar. This tripartite strategic convergence serves as the primary foundation that conditions the formation of an adaptive *Change Mechanism* to drive concrete steps in the form of *Business Process Redesign*. In line with the figure's descriptive notes, this visualization reinforces that bureaucratic reengineering does not stand alone, but is born from the harmonious interaction between the strength of actor agency, the readiness of institutional structures, and the supporting capacity of the socio-technical system. To complete the anatomy of the model, its adaptive and accommodative nature toward multi-actor networks provides organizational flexibility, although it is acknowledged that horizontal and vertical unification still progresses partially due to

sectoral regulatory restrictions or technological interoperability gaps between institutions.

Figure 6. Relationships Between Elements of the Empirical Model

Source: Processed Research Data, 2026

Theoretically, the governance transformation dynamics at the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP align with several scientific foundational thoughts within public administration discourse. The shift in service models from a conventional pattern toward an integrated digital ecosystem validates the *public service transformation* perspective, which posits that bureaucratic reform encompasses the restructuring of inter-organizational relations at a macro level. Obstacles in the form of persistent sectoral *backend* processes by each agency reflect Scott's (2014) *institutional theory* thesis regarding the tendency of public organizations to retain institutionalized, legacy workflows. The pressure of external technology disrupting bureaucratic stability conforms to Burke's (2017) change model concerning the dynamic interaction between the organizational environment and internal systems. Meanwhile, the central functionality of the DPMPTSP as the driving force for cross-sectoral relations affirms Agranoff and McGuire's (2003) *governance network* theory regarding the urgency of a formal coordinator.

A new dependency on server stability and field-level infrastructure readiness reflects the views of Bostrom and Heinen (1977) within the *socio-technical system* framework regarding the importance of alignment between human capacity and technology, while simultaneously triggering the *digital paradox* phenomenon and interoperability challenges as outlined by Mergel et al. (2019). To anticipate the rigidity of such formal systems, the existence of adaptive informal communication validates Ansell and Gash's (2008) concept of *adaptive governance*. The step-by-step integration process (*incremental integration*) chosen by the region to avoid service disruption also heavily corresponds with Lindblom's (1959) theory of *incremental change*. Conceptually, the *novelty* of this research lies in the development of a transformative empirical model based on socio-technical interactions, rather than merely a physical, administrative consolidation. Practically, this model possesses a high degree of *transferability* and

scalability to be replicated in other regions because it is formulated within the general categories of integrated public service governance in Indonesia.

CONCLUSIONS

The process of change and the mechanism of business process redesign in optimizing the Tulang Bawang Regency MPP services are proven to take place gradually (*incremental transformation*) through the implementation of a *hybrid governance mechanism*. This transformation moves dynamically from a conventional manual model to partial digitalization, and ultimately migrates toward the reform of work patterns based on cross-sectoral digital applications. In practice, this mechanism does not rely solely on formal bureaucratic procedures; rather, it is robustly supported by *adaptive coordination* through the utilization of informal communication channels (WhatsApp and direct phone calls) to overcome sectoral digital system dysfunctions or field-level verification delays. Through these adaptation mechanisms, business process redesign actions tangibly materialize through the simplification of stages, minimization of direct face-to-face contact, process standardization, and the phased adoption of electronic *approval* to prune past bureaucratic complexities.

This array of dynamics has been successfully formulated into a comprehensive, phased, and sustainable Empirical Model of Business Process Redesign Mechanisms Toward MPP Service Optimization. The conceptualization of this model constructs a dynamic causal relationship moving from the upstream problem to downstream optimization through seven circular stages, which include: *Initial Service Conditions* (baseline sectoral fragmentation), *Change Triggers* (regulatory pressures and efficiency demands), *Change Drivers* (mobilization of key actors/lead agency, institutions, and digitalization pressures), *Socio-Technical Systems* (alignment of human resources and technological infrastructure embedded with *enabling* and *constraining factors*), *Change Mechanisms* (formal-informal adaptive coordination), *Business Process Redesign* (workflow simplification and platform unification), leading up to the accumulation of *Outputs*, *Outcomes*, and *Long-Term Impacts*. This model scientifically proves that *service optimization* is not merely a technical-digital intervention. Instead, it must be constructed as a product of a harmonious, simultaneous interaction between the sociological capacity of actors, the legitimacy of institutional structures, and adaptive, inclusive digital technology interoperability, thereby holding high *novelty* and *transferability* value for replication in other regional MPP.

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